

Exploring the Rise of Indian Diasporic Writing in English

Dr. Tushar Nair

Career Point University

Corresponding author: tgnair@gmail.com

Abstract

The history of Indian diasporic writing is as old as the diaspora itself. Most of the Indian diaspora now settled in different countries found its inception in the form of indentured labour. The population of diaspora has increased over the years due to increased migration, a shift in global supply chain and technological advancements which together have shrunk the world so much so that the distances have melted and people can always be close to one-another. These things reflect very well in the works of Indian diasporic writers. These writers have taken the world by awe through their works. From Kamala Markandaya to Sunetra Gupta and from V. S. Naipaul to Rohinton Mistry, the Indian diasporic writers have carved out a niche for themselves in the terrain of world literature. They are winning awards and getting worldwide acceptance and acclaim. The themes of these writers involve- nostalgia, loss of identity, loss of culture, reinventing oneself, quest of self, rootlessness, alienation, homeland, amalgamation and assimilation and the other experiences, which come as part of settlement at a new place. Today in the changed scenario the idea of diaspora has got altogether changed. In the present world where there is more tolerance and acceptability, and distances have shrunk, making it a global village, the core themes do not have the poignance and acridness of experience which the early diasporic writers infused their works with in writing about issues and maladies pertaining to the Indian diaspora.